

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF Mn(II) AND Cd(II) COMPLEXES

Compounds	M.P. (°C)	Λ_M (mhos. cm ²)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	%metal		%sulfur		%nitrogen	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
MnL ₂ (β -pic) ₂	186	8.2	5.92	9.85	10.23	23.62	23.84	10.24	10.58
MnL ₂ Q ₂	198	9.4	5.95	8.91	9.02	20.82	21.02	8.82	9.2
MnL ₂ (Morph) ₂	215	8.6	5.95	10.22	10.47	24.11	24.39	10.35	10.67
CdL ₂ (β -pic)	7250	10.5	—	22.14	22.42	25.31	25.54	8.02	8.38
CdL ₂ Q	200	10.8	—	20.69	20.91	23.62	23.82	7.61	7.82
CdL ₂ (Morph.)	238	11.6	—	22.34	22.69	25.56	25.83	8.16	8.48
CdL ₂ Py	212	11.8	—	22.34	22.05	26.05	26.26	8.48	8.62

β -pic= β -picoline, Q=quinoline, Py=Pyridine, Morph=Morpholine.

$\frac{M}{1000}$ acetone solution, I.R. spectra were recorded in KBr phase in Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of Mn(II) complexes were studied using $\frac{M}{100}$ acetone solution using Hilger Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. Relevant data are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All the Mn(II) complexes have the general composition MnL₂B₂ and Cd(II) complexes are of the type CdL₂B, where L is diethyl dithiocarbamate and B is an amine viz. pyridine, β -picoline, quinoline and morpholine. These are white crystalline solids and have low molar conductance values in acetone, Λ_M being in the range of 8-12 mhos.cm² (Table 1) indicating non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Infrared spectra of dithiocarbamates have been studied earlier by Nakamoto et al⁵ and others⁶. Important characteristic bands viz. $\nu(C-N)$ and $\nu(C-S)$ could be easily assigned. In sodium diethyl dithiocarbamate $\nu(C-N)$, $\nu_{as}(C-S)$ and $\nu_s(C-S)$ occur⁶ at 1450, 890 and 1260 cm⁻¹ respectively. In Mn(II) and Cd(II) dithiocarbamates these bands appear ~1430, 880 and 1240 cm⁻¹ respectively. Shifting of these bands to lower frequency region indicates coordination through both the sulfur atoms. In the mixed ligand complexes these bands were observed ~1450, 890 and 1250 cm⁻¹. Shifting of these bands again to higher frequency region occurs due to the coordination of σ -bonding nitrogen donor ligands. In addition, most of the free nitrogen ligand absorption are shifted in the complexes indicating bonding to the metal ion. These have been further substantiated by observation of absorption bands ~260-300 and ~350-380 cm⁻¹ region attributable⁷ to $\nu(M-S)$ and $\nu(M-N)$ vibrations. Hence on the basis of these observations cadmium complexes are presumed to be penta-coordinated. In view of the spherical nature of the Cd(II) ion and the absence of crystal field effects, this is not entirely unexpected.

Mn(II) complexes show at least four absorption bands ~18.4-18.6, 22.6-22.8, 24.4-24.5 and 27.7 k.k. regions assignable⁸ to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, $\rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$,

$\rightarrow {}^4E_g$, $A_{1g}(G)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(D)$ transitions respectively. A high spin octahedral structure is suggested for these complexes. Magnetic moment values of 5.9-B.M. also supports this configuration.

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Mixed Ligand Diamine Complexes of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) with 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthaldehyde and Benzoylacetone

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A survey of the literature¹⁻³ has shown that no work has been done on the mixed ligand complexes of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and benzoylacetone. The mixed ligand complexes have been treated with diamines to get mixed diamine complexes.

NOTES

TABLE 1—MOLECULAR WEIGHT, ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND COLOUR OF THE MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES AND THE MIXED DIAMINE COMPLEXES OF Ni(II), Cu(II) AND Pd(II)

	Molecular wt. Found (Calc.)	Elemental analysis Found (Calc.)%				Colour
		C	H	N	M	
Mixed Ligand Complexes						
[Ni(C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₄)]	380(391)	65.82(65.45)	3.91(4.09)	—	15.00(15.10)	Red
[Cu(C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₄)]	388(396)	63.51(63.63)	3.90(4.04)	—	16.02(16.16)	Brown'sh red
[Pd(C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₄)]	429(438)	57.31(57.53)	3.52(3.65)	—	24.08(24.20)	Yellow
Mixed Ethylenediamine Complexes						
[Ni(C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂)]	403(415)	66.90(66.51)	4.64(4.81)	6.59(6.74)	14.02(14.19)	Yellow
[Cu(C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂)]	405(420)	65.48(65.74)	4.62(4.76)	6.56(6.66)	15.06(15.24)	Chocolate red
[Pd(C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂)]	450(462)	59.41(59.79)	4.23(4.32)	5.92(6.06)	22.81(22.95)	Yellow
Mixed Propylenediamine Complexes						
[Ni(C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂)]	415(429)	66.91(67.13)	5.00(5.12)	6.38(6.52)	13.53(13.75)	Dull yellow
[Cu(C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂)]	423(434)	66.13(66.36)	4.95(5.06)	6.31(6.42)	14.48(14.74)	Brick red
[Pd(C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂)]	462(476)	60.02(60.23)	4.50(4.62)	5.62(5.88)	22.05(22.27)	Yellow

The mixed ligand complexes of the type [MLL'], where M=Ni(II), Cu(II) or Pd(II), L=2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and L'=benzoylacetone, were prepared by adding both the ligands to the metal acetate solution in alcoholic medium in 1 : 1 : 1 mole ratio. After mixing, a coloured solid separated—which was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from chloroform. These compounds were analysed for their elements as shown in Table 1.

The mixed diamine complexes were prepared by adding an aqueous solution of ethylene- or propylenediamine to an alcoholic solution of the mixed ligand complex till pH 6 was attained. After 30-40 minutes, a coloured solid separated which was filtered, washed, and recrystallised from chloroform. In the alternative method, the mixed diamine complex was prepared by refluxing together for 2 hours the mixed ligand complex and ethylene- or propylenediamine in alcoholic medium. The solid diamine complex obtained was filtered, washed, recrystallised from chloroform, dried and analysed. The diamine complexes thus obtained by both the procedures are identical. All the mixed ligand complexes and mixed diamine complexes are coloured (as shown in Table 1) and do not possess sharp m.p. and they decompose above 230° without melting, giving oxides between 460-490°. Results of their elemental analyses are given in Table 1.

The mixed diamine complexes are soluble in organic solvents such as DMF, benzene, dioxan, nitrobenzene, chloroform, etc., but are insoluble in water.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the mixed diamine complexes suggest the diamagnetic nature of the Ni(II)- and Pd(II)-complexes⁴ and paramagnetic nature for the Cu(II)-complex⁵ (1.87 B.M.) at 303°K. The observed moment of the Cu(II) complex is close to the spin-only value for one unpaired electron.

The electronic absorption spectra of the mixed Ni(II)-diamine complex in benzene consist of two bands at 16600 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=228$ mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and 17800 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=302$ mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹) assignable to the transitions ¹A_{1g}→¹B_{1g} and ¹A_{1g}→¹E_g, respectively. The benzene solution of Cu(II)-complex gives only one band at 16200 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=198$ mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹), which may be assigned to the transition ²B_{1g}→²A_{1g}. Spectra of Pd(II)-complex exhibit three bands at 22500 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=164$ mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹), 26800 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=269$ mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and 30800 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=354$ mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹) which may be assigned to the transition ¹A_{1g}→¹B_{1g}, ¹A_{1g}→¹E_{1g} and ¹A_{1g}→¹A_{2u}, respectively. These data suggest square-planar configurations⁶⁻⁸ of the Ni(II)-, Cu(II)- and Pd(II)-diamine complexes. Thus the mixed ligand functions as a tetradentate ligand in all the three metal complexes of interest.

The negligibly small values ($\Lambda_M=4.0-6.5$ ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹) of molar conductance of the mixed ligand diamine complexes in DMF suggest them to be neutral in nature (Fig. 1).

where M=Ni(II), Cu(II) or Pd(II), R=H or OH,

Fig. 1. Mixed Ligand Diamine Complexes of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II)

The I.R. spectra of all the diamine complexes do not exhibit any band around 3410 cm⁻¹ indicating that hydrogen of the -OH groups of benzoylacetone and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, get dissociated on complexation. These complexes gave three bands

in the narrow ranges of 1590-1580, 600-580 and 540-525 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$, $\nu\text{M}-\text{O}$ and $\nu\text{M}-\text{N}$ bondings, respectively. Thus the mixed ligand diamine complexes may be represented by the structure as shown in Fig. 1.

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Formation Constants of the Complexes of 2-Benzofuran Glyoxylaldehyde Dioxime with Some Divalent Metal Ions

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THE formation constants of the complexes of 2-benzofuran glyoxylaldehyde dioxime with Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} have been calculated by pH-metric method at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ ($\mu=0.25 \text{ NaClO}_4$). It has also been shown to form 1 : 2 complexes. The trend in the stability constant values of these metal chelates has been found to be $\text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$.

A survey of the literature revealed that pH-metric studies of Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} with 2-benzofuran glyoxylaldehyde dioxime have not so far been described. In view of the above, it was considered of interest to make the study of these systems potentiometrically.

Experimental

All the metal perchlorate solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. Metal ions other

than UO_2^{2+} were standardized complexometrically by EDTA titrations². UO_2^{2+} was estimated by precipitating with ammonia and weighing it as U_3O_8 after igniting the precipitate in a platinum crucible. The ligand solution was prepared in purified methanol.

Systronics pH-meter standardized against a 0.05M solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate (AR, BDH) was used for all the pH-measurements. The glass electrode was kept for several days immersed in the methanol before use as recommended by Zeidler³. The following solutions (total volume 20 ml) at $\mu=0.25 \text{ NaClO}_4$ (NaClO_4 prepared in methanol) and temperature $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$, were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution (0.1M).

(i) 10.00 ml (0.025M) ligand + 5.00 ml (1.00 M) NaClO_4 + 5.00 ml redistilled water.

(ii) 10.00 ml (0.025M) ligand + 1.00 ml (0.025M) $\text{Mn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O} / \text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O} / \text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} / \text{UO}_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ + 5.00 ml (1.00 M) NaClO_4 + 4.00 ml redistilled water.

The medium of titration was 75 : 25 per cent methanol water (v/v)*. All the titrations of the ligand with and without the presence of metal solutions were performed according to the method of Calvin and Melchior⁴.

Results and Discussion

The dissociation constant (pK) of the ligand was determined by pH-titrations following the method of Bjerrum⁴. It is found out from the formation curve obtained by plotting pH against $\bar{n}H$ values (where $\bar{n}H$ = average number of hydrogen ions attached to a ligand ion) as pH, where $\bar{n}H=0.5$ and comes out to be 10.85.

A comparison of pH titration curves of ligand with and without metal ions indicate that the curves for ligand containing metal ions run much below the curve for ligand. The lowering of the curves for binary systems with respect to ligand takes place from the very beginning of the titration. The analysis of the potentiometric data for these systems also shows that the formation of chelate occurs through successive formation. The horizontal distance between the two titration curves obtained with the solutions (i) and (ii) at any value of pH gives the amount of proton liberated by chelation, i.e., the amount of ligand complexed. This value divided by the total concentration of all metal species in the system gave $\bar{n}$. This may be written as

$$\bar{n} = \frac{C_A - [A]}{C_M}$$

where C_A = total concentration of ligand species

* For correspondence.